

Model UN Environment Programme
شبه سازی برنامه محیط زیست سازمان ملل متحد
د ملگرو ملتونو د چاپیریال پروگرام ماډل

Organisation of Green Future Afghanistan
موسسه آینده سبز افغانستان
د افغانستان د زرغون راتلونکی موسسه

INTERNATIONAL MODEL UNITED NATIONS CONFERENCE- 2024 (STUDENTS' COP 30 IN AFGHANISTAN)

Agenda: Critical discussions are anticipated to revolve around various topics, including Green Economics, Smart City Planning, the Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Environmental Protection, Intellectual Property and Environment, Sustainable Development and inclusion of Environmental Protection in International Investment Treaty Provisions.

DIGNITARIES

CHIEF GUEST

Dr. N. Vanishree
Professor of Law
Chairman of Post Graduate
JSS Law College, Autonomous, Mysore
Karnataka, India

GUEST OF HONOR

Prof. Banu M.
Assistant Professor of Computer Science
St Joseph University,
Bengaluru-560027, Karnataka, India

JUDGES

Dr. SRIDEVI KRISHNA
Professor of International Law
Vidyavardhaka Law College
Sheshadri Iyer Road, New Bamboo
Bazar, Mysuru – 570001, Karnataka,
India

ORGANIZING MEMBERS

- Ms. Qadria Hashimi, CEO, Founding Member
Organisation of Green Future Afghanistan and
student of the Institute of Legal and Policy Research
- Ms. Basmia Asghary, Founding Member
Organisation of Green Future Afghanistan and
student of the Institute of Legal and Policy Research
- Ms. Bahara Kaihan, Founding Member
Organisation of Green Future Afghanistan and
student of the Institute of Legal and Policy Research
- Ms. Hasina Rassuli, Founding Member
Organisation of Green Future Afghanistan and
student of the Institute of Legal and Policy Research

EXECUTIVE BOARD MEMBER

Ms. Mrunalini Dnyaneshwar Borkar
Chairperson
Model United Nations Conference &
St Xavier's High School, MIDC NAGPUR,

Ms. Saba Firdose
Rapporteur,

Model United Nations Conference &
Student of LLM, Department of Studies in
Law, University of Mysore.

Contact Information

For inquiries and participation
confirmation, please contact the
following undersigned:

Ms. Qadriya Hashimi
CEO

Organisation of Green Future Afghanistan
Email: qadriahashimi64@gmail.com
info@ogfaf.org

Event: 4th May, 2024.
Participants: Participation is open
exclusively to females worldwide.
Format & Platform: Webex (Online)
Registration Fees: None (This event is free of
charge)

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INTERNATIONAL MODEL UNITED NATIONS CONFERENCE- 2024 (STUDENTS' COP 30 IN AFGHANISTAN)

BACKGROUND GUIDE

Prefatory Note

The Conference of the Parties (COP) stands as the apex body entrusted with the pivotal responsibility of steering the course of action for the Convention. Comprising representatives from all States party to the Convention, the COP convenes to meticulously evaluate the progress and execution of the Convention's mandates. Within its purview lies the scrutiny of national communications and emission inventories furnished by the Parties. This data serves as the bedrock upon which assessments are built regarding the efficacy of measures adopted by Parties and the strides made towards realizing the Convention's overarching objectives. Convening annually, unless specified otherwise by the Parties, the COP serves as a beacon of collective determination in the global fight against climate change. Its inaugural session, held in Berlin, Germany in March 1995, marked the commencement of a concerted effort to address environmental challenges on a unified platform. Typically headquartered in Bonn, the seat of the secretariat, the COP occasionally relocates to other hosting nations, thereby symbolizing a spirit of inclusivity and shared responsibility. As the mantle of COP Presidency rotates among the five recognized UN regions, mirroring a commitment to equitable representation, so too does the venue of its gatherings traverse these diverse geographical terrains. From Africa to Asia, Latin America and the Caribbean, Central and Eastern Europe, and Western Europe and Others, the COP transcends borders to foster global cooperation and solidarity in the pursuit of sustainable development and environmental preservation.

CHRONOLOGY OF CONFERENCE OF THE PARTIES (COP)

COP ONE

The first Conference of the Parties to the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change convened in Berlin from March 28th to April 7th, 1995.¹ Delegates from 117 Parties and 53 observer States gathered in a city once divided by the Cold War, recognizing persistent

¹ Paul E. Hagen et al., *International Environmental Law*, 31 INT. LAWYER 627 (1997).

challenges despite the fall of physical barriers. COP-1 witnessed intense negotiations on commitments, culminating in a mandate to outline actions beyond 2000.

COP TWO

The Stockholm Convention on Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs), held in May 2001 in Sweden, was a crucial moment in global environmental law.² Representatives from around the world gathered to address the dangers posed by POPs, toxic chemicals that persist in the environment. The convention aimed to regulate and phase out twelve priority POPs, such as DDT and PCBs, through regulatory measures and international collaboration. Despite progress, challenges like ongoing POPs use and emergence of similar chemicals persist, highlighting the need for sustained international cooperation to ensure a healthier, more sustainable future.

COP THREE

The Kyoto Climate Change Conference in December 1997,³ it was a pivotal moment in global efforts to combat climate change. The conference saw the negotiation and adoption of the Kyoto Protocol, setting emission reduction targets for six greenhouse gases over 2008-2012. The protocol introduced flexible mechanisms like emissions trading, CDM, and JI to facilitate compliance and sustainable development, especially in developing nations. Despite challenges, such as the US withdrawal, it laid the groundwork for international cooperation, leading to subsequent agreements like the Paris Agreement in 2015, emphasizing multilateralism in tackling climate change.

COP FOUR

The Buenos Aires Climate Change Conference in November 1998, hosted under the UNFCCC, was a significant event in global climate action.⁴ Delegates from around the world convened to discuss the implementation of the Kyoto Protocol, focusing on emissions reduction targets and financial mechanisms. While no major breakthroughs were achieved, the conference laid the groundwork for future negotiations, highlighting the ongoing commitment to address climate change on a global scale.

COP FIVE

The Bonn Climate Change Conference in October 1999, hosted by the UNFCCC, was pivotal in advancing global efforts against climate change.⁵ Delegates convened to push forward the

² Peter L. Lallas, *The Stockholm Convention on Persistent Organic Pollutants*, 95 AM. J. INT. LAW 692 (2001).

³ Jon C. Lovett, *1997 Kyoto Protocol*, 49 J. AFR. LAW 94 (2005).

⁴ SALEEMUL HUQ, *Adaptation to Climate Change: A Paper for the International Climate Change Taskforce*, (2005), <https://www.jstor.org/stable/resrep16058> (last visited Mar 22, 2024).

⁵ SALEEMUL HUQ, HANNAH REID & LAUREL A. MURRAY, *Climate Change and Development Links*, (2006), <https://www.jstor.org/stable/resrep01331> (last visited Mar 22, 2024).

implementation of the Kyoto Protocol, focusing on crucial issues like emissions trading and compliance mechanisms. Despite challenges, agreements were reached, highlighting the importance of international cooperation. The conference laid the groundwork for future climate action, emphasizing the possibility of nations working together to confront this shared challenge.

COP SIX

The Hague Climate Change Conference in November 2000 aimed to refine and advance the Kyoto Protocol's implementation but ended in a deadlock due to disagreements, notably between the EU and the US, over carbon sinks' inclusion in emissions reduction targets.⁶ Despite intense negotiations, no consensus was reached, dealing a blow to international efforts. The conference underscored the complexities of climate negotiations and emphasized the need for continued dialogue and cooperation to address climate change effectively.

COP SIX- TWO

The Bonn Climate Change Conference in July 2001, hosted by the UNFCCC, was pivotal in reviving efforts to implement the Kyoto Protocol after the Hague's setback.⁷ Key achievements included resolving the contentious issue of carbon sinks and finalizing the protocol's rulebook. Delegates balanced environmental integrity with flexibility, reaching agreements on emissions trading and compliance. The conference demonstrated international resilience and cooperation in addressing climate change, marking a significant step forward in global efforts to combat this pressing challenge.

COP SEVEN

The Marrakech Climate Change Conference in October 2001,⁸ under the UNFCCC, built on Bonn's progress earlier that year, advancing the Kyoto Protocol's implementation. Delegates focused on finalizing the protocol's rulebook, resolving disputes, and enhancing agreements on emissions trading and clean development mechanisms. The conference's major achievement was clarity in protocol implementation. Additionally, it mobilized support for developing nations through the Marrakech Accords, outlining financial aid and technology transfer mechanisms. The conference showcased global commitment to collective climate action, paving the way for further progress in addressing climate change.

⁶ Nadia von Bassewitz, *International Climate Change Policy: Where Do We Stand?*, in CLIMATE CHANGE: INTERNATIONAL LAW AND GLOBAL GOVERNANCE 101 (Oliver C. Ruppel, Christian Roschmann, & Katharina Ruppel-Schlichting eds., 1 ed. 2013), <https://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctv941vsk.9> (last visited Mar 22, 2024).

⁷ Matthew Vespa, *Climate Change 2001: Kyoto at Bonn and Marrakech*, 29 *ECOL. LAW Q.* 395 (2002).

⁸ *Id.*

COP EIGHT

The New Delhi Climate Change Conference in October 2002, organized by the UNFCCC, convened representatives from across the globe to address climate change.⁹ With a focus on implementing the Kyoto Protocol, discussions centered on reviewing emissions reduction progress and enhancing compliance. Emphasis was placed on supporting developing countries in transitioning to low-carbon economies through increased financial and technical assistance. Additionally, the conference stressed the importance of engaging stakeholders beyond governments, highlighting the need for inclusive collaboration involving local communities, civil society, and the private sector.

COP NINE

The Milan Climate Change Conference in December 2003, under the UNFCCC, marked a significant step in global climate action.¹⁰ Representatives from nations worldwide gathered to strengthen the Kyoto Protocol's implementation, focusing on emissions reduction targets and enhancing mechanisms like emissions trading. Additionally, discussions addressed broader issues such as adaptation, technology transfer, and financial aid for vulnerable countries. The conference emphasized the need for inclusive international cooperation beyond the Kyoto Protocol, recognizing the importance of engaging all countries, including major emitters and developing economies, in efforts to combat climate change.

COP TEN

The Buenos Aires Climate Change Conference in December 2004 was a pivotal event in the global fight against climate change.¹¹ Representatives from nations worldwide gathered to discuss strategies, particularly focusing on implementing the Kyoto Protocol. Delegates grappled with challenges like emissions reduction and balancing economic interests, especially for developing countries. Despite no major breakthroughs, the conference highlighted the urgent need for action, driven by mounting scientific evidence. It also fostered engagement from various stakeholders beyond governments. While it laid groundwork for future negotiations, it underscored the imperative for international cooperation in addressing this pressing issue. Reflecting on the conference serves as a reminder of progress made and the

⁹ E. Lisa F. Schipper & Emily Boyd, *UNFCCC COP 11 and COP/MOP 1: At Last, Some Hope?*, 15 J. ENVIRON. DEV. 75 (2006).

¹⁰ K. Ya. Kondratyev & Kirill Kondratyev, *Key Aspects of Global Climate Change*, 15 ENERGY ENVIRON. 469 (2004).

¹¹ MOHAN J. DUTTA, VOICES OF RESISTANCE: COMMUNICATION AND SOCIAL CHANGE (DGO-Digital original ed. 2012), <https://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctt6wq6pw> (last visited Mar 22, 2024).

ongoing challenges ahead, calling for renewed efforts from governments, businesses, and individuals to ensure a sustainable future.

COP ELEVEN

The Montreal Climate Change Conference in December 2005 marked a pivotal moment in the global effort to combat climate change.¹² Building on the momentum of previous negotiations, such as the Kyoto Protocol, the conference focused on shaping future international climate agreements beyond 2012. Key outcomes included the launch of negotiations for a post-2012 climate regime and increased recognition of adaptation measures for vulnerable communities. The conference also highlighted the vital role of non-state actors, emphasizing multi-level governance and collaboration. While significant progress was made, challenges like defining emissions reduction targets and financing mechanisms persisted. Ultimately, the Montreal Conference underscored the collective determination to address climate change and the need for sustained cooperation and innovation to protect the planet for current and future generations.

COP TWELVE

The Nairobi Climate Change Conference in November 2006 was a crucial milestone in global efforts to address climate change.¹³ It convened representatives from nations worldwide to tackle urgent issues such as emissions reduction targets, adaptation measures, and financial assistance for developing countries. A significant outcome was the launch of the Nairobi Work Programme on Impacts, Vulnerability, and Adaptation to Climate Change, focusing on supporting adaptation efforts in vulnerable nations. The conference emphasized the importance of integrating climate considerations into sustainable development practices and promoted multi-stakeholder collaboration to exchange knowledge and best practices. Despite challenges, the conference underscored the international commitment to collective action against climate change.

COP THIRTEEN

The Bali Climate Change Conference in December 2007 was a pivotal event in the global response to climate change.¹⁴ It focused on negotiating a successor agreement to the Kyoto Protocol, which was set to expire in 2012. The conference resulted in the adoption of the Bali Road Map, outlining a two-year process for post-2012 agreement negotiations. Key outcomes

¹² Cass R. Sunstein, *On the Divergent American Reactions to Terrorism and Climate Change*, 107 COLUMBIA LAW REV. 503 (2007).

¹³ von Bassewitz, *supra* note 6.

¹⁴ Reid Basher, *Disaster Impacts: Implications and Policy Responses*, 75 SOC. RES. 937 (2008).

included the Bali Action Plan addressing mitigation, adaptation, technology transfer, and financing. The conference also emphasized the importance of addressing deforestation, leading to the establishment of the Bali Action Plan on Forests. Civil society engagement was notable, advocating for ambitious climate action. While progress was made, challenges like emissions reductions, financial support, and legal aspects persisted in subsequent negotiations.

COP FOURTEEN

The Poznań Climate Change Conference in December 2008 was pivotal in advancing global efforts against climate change.¹⁵ Representatives from nations worldwide convened to address key issues like emission reduction targets, financing mechanisms, and technology transfer. Despite complexities, the conference made progress, setting a structured work plan for negotiations towards the Copenhagen Climate Change Conference in 2009. Emphasis was placed on adaptation measures and technology transfer, laying the groundwork for future cooperation. Challenges persisted, requiring continued engagement to achieve a comprehensive global climate agreement.

COP FIFTEEN

The Copenhagen Climate Change Conference in December 2009 was a crucial gathering of world leaders and stakeholders aimed at forging a new global climate agreement.¹⁶ Despite high expectations, the conference did not produce a legally binding agreement due to deep divides between developed and developing nations. However, it resulted in the Copenhagen Accord, a political agreement outlining voluntary emissions reduction targets and provisions for financial assistance to developing countries. While falling short of expectations, the Copenhagen Accord represented a significant step forward in the global climate effort, signaling renewed commitment and laying the groundwork for future negotiations. The conference underscored the importance of continued dialogue and cooperation among nations in addressing climate change and highlighted the need for increased ambition and urgency in tackling this pressing issue.

COP SIXTEEN

The Cancún Climate Change Conference in November 2010 was a significant step forward in global efforts to combat climate change.¹⁷ Representatives from countries worldwide convened in Cancún, Mexico, aiming to build on the challenges faced at the Copenhagen Conference.

¹⁵ KATHERINE MICHONSKI & MICHAEL A. LEVI, *Harnessing International Institutions to Address Climate Change*, (2010), <https://www.jstor.org/stable/resrep00271> (last visited Mar 22, 2024).

¹⁶ Daniel Bodansky, *The Copenhagen Climate Change Conference: A Postmortem*, 104 AM. J. INT. LAW 230 (2010).

¹⁷ Martin Khor, *Complex Implications of the Cancun Climate Conference*, 45 ECON. POLIT. WKLY. 10 (2010).

Unlike Copenhagen, Cancún saw a more collaborative approach, resulting in the adoption of the Cancún Agreements. These agreements focused on key issues such as emissions reduction targets, adaptation measures, and financing mechanisms. Key outcomes included the establishment of the Green Climate Fund and provisions for enhanced transparency in reporting emissions. The conference reaffirmed commitments to limit global temperature rise and emphasized inclusivity by engaging with non-state actors. Overall, Cancún brought renewed hope for international cooperation in addressing climate change.

COP SEVENTEEN

The Durban Climate Change Conference in November 2011 was pivotal in shaping the global response to climate change.¹⁸ Representatives from nations worldwide convened in Durban, South Africa, to negotiate a new climate agreement, aiming for ambitious emissions reduction targets. A key outcome was the adoption of the Durban Platform for Enhanced Action, laying the groundwork for future negotiations. Progress was also made with the establishment of the Green Climate Fund and agreement on a second commitment period for the Kyoto Protocol. The conference underscored the importance of addressing the needs of vulnerable countries and communities, although challenges persisted in subsequent negotiations.

COP EIGHTEEN

The Doha Climate Change Conference in November 2012 marked a crucial step in global efforts to address climate change.¹⁹ Representatives from nations worldwide gathered in Doha, Qatar, to negotiate a new phase of the Kyoto Protocol, aiming to strengthen the global response to climate change. A significant outcome was the agreement to extend the Kyoto Protocol for a second commitment period until 2020, demonstrating continued commitment to emissions reductions. Progress was also made on key issues such as the operationalization of the Green Climate Fund and the adoption of the Doha Amendment, outlining emission reduction targets. The conference emphasized the importance of addressing the needs of developing countries, particularly in terms of adaptation and support. However, challenges remained, including achieving consensus on ambitious emissions reduction targets and securing adequate funding for climate action.

¹⁸ Oliver C. Ruppel, *Intersections of Law and Cooperative Global Climate Governance – Challenges in the Anthropocene*, in CLIMATE CHANGE: INTERNATIONAL LAW AND GLOBAL GOVERNANCE 29 (Oliver C. Ruppel, Christian Roschmann, & Katharina Ruppel-Schlichting eds., 1 ed. 2013), <https://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctv941w8s.8> (last visited Mar 22, 2024).

¹⁹ CLARE DEMERSE & P.J. PARTINGTON, *UN Climate Negotiations in Doha, Qatar*, (2012), <https://www.jstor.org/stable/resrep00203> (last visited Mar 22, 2024).

COP NINETEEN

The Warsaw Climate Change Conference in November 2013 was pivotal in advancing global efforts to combat climate change.²⁰ Representatives from nations worldwide convened in Warsaw, Poland, to negotiate key elements for the 2015 Paris Agreement, focusing on emissions reduction targets, adaptation measures, financing, and technology transfer. A notable outcome was the establishment of the Warsaw International Mechanism for Loss and Damage, aiming to assist vulnerable countries affected by climate-related disasters. Progress was also made on operationalizing the Green Climate Fund and enhancing transparency in reporting emissions. The conference emphasized engaging non-state actors to strengthen partnerships. However, challenges remained, including the ambition of emissions reduction targets and financial support for developing countries.

COP TWENTY

The Lima Climate Change Conference in December 2014 was a pivotal moment in global efforts to address climate change.²¹ The conference laid the groundwork for the Paris Agreement, focusing on key issues such as emissions reduction targets, adaptation measures, and climate finance. A significant outcome was the adoption of the Lima Call for Climate Action, which established a framework for countries to submit their climate targets. The conference emphasized the role of non-state actors and showcased innovative solutions to climate challenges. While challenges remained, Lima set the stage for the historic Paris Agreement, demonstrating global commitment to combatting climate change.

COP TWENTY-ONE

The Paris Climate Change Conference in November 2015 was a pivotal moment in the global fight against climate change.²² Nearly 200 countries negotiated a comprehensive and ambitious international climate agreement. The conference aimed to limit global temperature rise to well below 2 degrees Celsius, with efforts towards a more ambitious target of 1.5 degrees Celsius. The resulting Paris Agreement, adopted on December 12, 2015, is legally binding and universal, requiring all signatory parties to take action to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and enhance climate resilience. Key elements include nationally determined contributions (NDCs), transparency and accountability frameworks, and provisions for financial assistance to support developing countries. The agreement recognizes the principle of common but differentiated

²⁰ KJELL ENGELBREKT, *HIGH-TABLE DIPLOMACY: THE RESHAPING OF INTERNATIONAL SECURITY INSTITUTIONS* (2016), <https://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctt1c84cd2> (last visited Mar 22, 2024).

²¹ *Id.*

²² Harry van der Linden, *Climate Change Mitigation and the U.N. Security Council: A Just War Analysis*, in *PACIFISM, POLITICS, AND FEMINISM* 117 (Jennifer Kling ed., 2019), <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.1163/j.ctv2gjwx12.11> (last visited Mar 22, 2024).

responsibilities and emphasizes equity and sustainable development. The Paris Conference witnessed unprecedented cooperation among nations and active engagement from non-state actors. However, its success depends on the full implementation of its provisions by all parties, highlighting the need for continued cooperation, innovation, and commitment to secure a sustainable future.

COP TWENTY-TWO

The Marrakech Climate Change Conference in November 2016 was pivotal in the global response to climate change.²³ The conference focused on implementing the Paris Agreement's ambitious goals. Delegates from nearly 200 countries reaffirmed their commitment to limiting global temperature rise and increasing efforts to achieve this. Key outcomes included the Marrakech Action Proclamation, emphasizing urgency and cooperation, and the launch of initiatives to enhance climate resilience and promote renewable energy. The conference highlighted the role of non-state actors in driving climate action. While progress was made, challenges such as increasing ambition in emissions reductions and providing adequate financial support for developing countries remained. Nonetheless, Marrakech demonstrated ongoing commitment to collective climate action and laid the groundwork for future progress.

COP TWENTY-THREE

The UN Climate Change Conference in November 2017, also known as COP 23, held in Bonn, Germany, was pivotal in advancing global efforts to combat climate change.²⁴ Delegates focused on accelerating progress towards the goals outlined in the Paris Agreement, emphasizing enhancing ambition in emissions reductions, promoting climate resilience, and supporting developing countries. A significant outcome was the launch of the Talanoa Dialogue, fostering collaboration and understanding among nations to increase climate action ambition. Progress was made on operationalizing mechanisms like the Green Climate Fund, enhancing transparency, and engaging non-state actors in climate action. Despite challenges, the conference highlighted the international community's commitment to addressing climate change and laid the groundwork for further advancements.

²³ David Belis et al., *China, the United States and the European Union: Multiple Bilateralism and Prospects for a New Climate Change Diplomacy*, 9 CARBON CLIM. LAW REV. 203 (2015).

²⁴ PATRÍCIA GALVÃO FERREIRA, *Climate Finance Obligations: Continuities*, 4 (2018), <https://www.jstor.org/stable/resrep24962.8> (last visited Mar 22, 2024).

COP TWENTY-FOUR

The Katowice Climate Change Conference in December 2018, known as COP 24, was pivotal in advancing global climate action.²⁵ Delegates from nations worldwide gathered to finalize guidelines for implementing the Paris Agreement, focusing on transparency and accountability. A key outcome was the adoption of the Katowice Climate Package, establishing rules for reporting emissions and ensuring accountability. Progress was made on climate finance, with commitments to support developing countries. The conference highlighted the role of non-state actors in driving climate action. While significant strides were made, challenges remain in increasing emission reductions and supporting vulnerable countries. Nonetheless, the conference demonstrated a collective commitment to addressing climate change effectively.

COP TWENTY-FIVE

The COP 25 UN Climate Change Conference convened in Madrid, Spain, in December 2019, representing a pivotal moment in global climate efforts.²⁶ Delegates aimed to strengthen commitments under the Paris Agreement, striving to limit global temperature rise to below 2 degrees Celsius, with a push for a more ambitious 1.5-degree target. However, disputes over issues like carbon markets and finance hindered substantial progress. Nonetheless, COP 25 showcased initiatives to reduce emissions, promote renewable energy, and enhance resilience. Despite falling short of expectations, the conference emphasized the urgent need for heightened ambition and collaboration across all levels to address climate change and safeguard the planet for future generations.

COP TWENTY-SIX

The Glasgow Climate Change Conference, or COP26, held in October-November 2021, Conference marked a pivotal moment in the global fight against climate change.²⁷ Nearly 200 countries gathered to strengthen the implementation of the Paris Agreement and accelerate efforts to limit global warming to well below 2 degrees Celsius. Significant commitments were made to achieve net-zero emissions and increase support for vulnerable nations. Despite falling short of some expectations, the Glasgow Climate Pact outlined specific actions and commitments, providing a framework for continued collaboration and action in the years ahead.

²⁵ KIRSTEN E H JENKINS, *Implementing Just Transition After Cop24*, (2019), <https://www.jstor.org/stable/resrep21725> (last visited Mar 22, 2024).

²⁶ Gregg B. Walker, *Confronting Complex Global Challenges: Comparing the Climate Change and Law of the Sea Negotiations*, in CLIMATE CHANGE: INTERNATIONAL LAW AND GLOBAL GOVERNANCE 275 (Oliver C. Ruppel, Christian Roschmann, & Katharina Ruppel-Schlichting eds., 1 ed. 2013), <https://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctv941vsk.15> (last visited Mar 22, 2024).

²⁷ *Id.*

COP TWENTY-SEVEN

COP 27, hosted by Egypt in November 2022, aimed to bolster global climate action.²⁸ It provided a forum to strengthen the Paris Agreement's implementation, promote renewable energy, and support vulnerable communities. Key objectives included enhancing international cooperation on climate finance and technology transfer, while ensuring inclusive participation and addressing the needs of vulnerable groups.

COP TWENTY-EIGHT

The COP28 UN Climate Change Conference in Dubai, UAE, was historic, with over 85,000 participants, including over 150 Heads of State and Government, attending from November 30 to December 13, 2023.²⁹ One significant outcome was the conclusion of the first global stocktake under the Paris Agreement. It revealed insufficient progress across all areas of climate action, prompting countries to agree on accelerating efforts by 2030. This includes transitioning from fossil fuels to renewables like wind and solar power, emphasizing the urgency of addressing climate change.

COP TWENTY-NINE

The 2024 UN Climate Change Conference (UNFCCC COP 29) is scheduled to take place in November in Baku, Azerbaijan.³⁰ This significant event will encompass the 29th session of the Conference of the Parties (COP 29), the 19th meeting of the COP serving as the Meeting of the Parties to the Kyoto Protocol (CMP 19), and the sixth meeting of the COP serving as the Meeting of the Parties to the Paris Agreement (CMA 6).

Key agenda items include finalizing the first enhanced transparency framework and establishing a new collective quantified goal on finance. Additionally, the 61st sessions of the Subsidiary Body for Scientific and Technological Advice (SBSTA 61) and the Subsidiary Body for Implementation (SBI 61) will convene to address pertinent climate-related matters.

COP TWENTY-THIRTY

The 2025 UN Climate Change Conference (UNFCCC COP 30) is scheduled to convene in November in Brazil.³¹ This significant gathering will encompass the 30th session of the

²⁸ ROMY CHEVALLIER & DANIELLE MARAIS, *Ensuring That COP27 Is Truly an 'African COP,'* (2022), <https://www.jstor.org/stable/resrep44021> (last visited Mar 22, 2024).

²⁹ ROMY CHEVALLIER ET AL., *Africa's Climate Champions: Keycountries to Watch at COP28,* (2023), <https://www.jstor.org/stable/resrep55042> (last visited Mar 22, 2024).

³⁰ UN Climate Change Conference Baku - November 2024 | UNFCCC, <https://unfccc.int/cop29> (last visited Mar 22, 2024).

³¹ IISD's SDG Knowledge Hub, *Event: 2025 UN Climate Change Conference (UNFCCC COP 30) | SDG Knowledge Hub | IISD*, <http://sdg.iisd.org/events/2025-un-climate-change-conference-unfccc-cop-30/> (last visited Mar 22, 2024).

Conference of the Parties (COP 30), the 20th meeting of the COP serving as the Meeting of the Parties to the Kyoto Protocol (CMP 20), and the seventh meeting of the COP serving as the Meeting of the Parties to the Paris Agreement (CMA 7). Additionally, the 63rd sessions of the Subsidiary Body for Scientific and Technological Advice (SBSTA 63) and the Subsidiary Body for Implementation (SBI 63) will also take place during this event. Key discussions are expected to focus on advancing the implementation of climate commitments, enhancing transparency and accountability mechanisms, and mobilizing increased financial and technological support for climate action worldwide.

A Glance to Chronology of COP1 to COP30.

SL No.	CONFERENCE OF THE PARTIES – SESSION	LOCATION & HOST STATE	CONFERENCE
01	COP 1	Berlin, Germany	Berlin, Germany in March, 1995
02	COP 2	Geneva, Switzerland	Geneva, Switzerland from 1 to 5 May 2006
03	COP 3	Kyoto, Japan	Kyoto Climate Change Conference - December 1997
04	COP 4	Buenos Aires, Argentina	Buenos Aires Climate Change Conference - November 1998
05	COP 5	Bonn, Germany	Bonn Climate Change Conference - October 1999
06	COP 6-2	The Hague, Netherlands	The Hague Climate Change Conference - November 2000
07	COP 6	Bonn, Germany	Bonn Climate Change Conference - July 2001
08	COP 7	Marrakech, Morocco	Marrakech Climate Change Conference - October 2001
09	COP 8	New Delhi, India	New Delhi Climate Change Conference - October 2002
10	COP 9	Milan, Italy	Milan Climate Change Conference - December 2003

11	COP 10	Buenos Aires, Argentina	Buenos Aires Climate Change Conference - December 2004
12	COP 11	Montreal, Canada	Montreal Climate Change Conference - December 2005
13	COP 12	Nairobi, Kenya	Nairobi Climate Change Conference - November 2006
14	COP 13	Bali, Indonesia	Bali Climate Change Conference - December 2007
15	COP 14	Poznan, Poland	Poznan Climate Change Conference - December 2008
16	COP 15	Copenhagen, Denmark	Copenhagen Climate Change Conference - December 2009
17	COP 16	Cancun, Mexico	Cancún Climate Change Conference - November 2010
18	COP 17	Durban, South Africa	Durban Climate Change Conference - November 2011
19	COP 18	Doha, Qatar	Doha Climate Change Conference - November 2012
20	COP 19	Warsaw, Poland	Warsaw Climate Change Conference - November 2013
21	COP 20	Lima, Peru	Lima Climate Change Conference - December 2014
22	COP 21	Paris, France	Paris Climate Change Conference - November 2015
23	COP 22	Marrakech, Morocco	Marrakech Climate Change Conference - November 2016
24	COP 23	Bonn, Germany	UN Climate Change Conference - November 2017
25	COP 24	Katowice, Poland	Katowice Climate Change Conference – December 2018
26	COP 25	Madrid, Spain	UN Climate Change Conference - December 2019

27	COP 26	Glasgow, UK	Glasgow Climate Change Conference – October- November 2021
28	COP 27	Sharm el-Sheikh, Egypt	Sharm el-Sheikh Climate Change Conference - November 2022
29	COP 28	Dubai, the United Arab Emirates	UN Climate Change Conference in Dubai, the United Arab Emirates, 30 November to 13 .December 2023
30	COP 29	Baku, Azerbaijan	Baku, Azerbaijan, Mon, 11 Nov, 2024 – Sun, 24 Nov, 2024
31	COP 30	Brazil	November 2025
	STUDENTS' COP 30	Kabul, Afghanistan	May 4, 2024.

STUDENTS COP 30 IN AFGHANISTAN

In organizing the COP30 simulation, the Organisation of Green Future Afghanistan aims to empower **'Girls Students'** to become catalysts for change within their communities and beyond. By immersing themselves in the complexities of international environmental negotiations, students not only broaden their understanding of global issues but also develop critical thinking skills and empathy towards differing perspectives.

The COP30 simulation serves as a microcosm of the real-world challenges faced by nations striving to mitigate climate change and promote sustainable development. Through research, negotiation, and consensus-building, participants learn the importance of collaboration and compromise in addressing complex environmental issues. Moreover, the simulation provides a platform for students to voice their concerns, propose innovative solutions, and advocate for policies that prioritize environmental protection and equity. As future leaders, students play a pivotal role in shaping the trajectory of our planet's environmental health. By equipping them with the knowledge and skills gained through simulations like COP30, the Organisation of Green Future Afghanistan endeavours to inspire a new girl's generation of environmental champions who are committed to building a more sustainable and resilient world for all.

THEME OF STUDENTS' COP30

The 2024 Students' Climate Change Conference (SCOP 30) in Afghanistan is poised to be a transformative event, scheduled to commence on Saturday, May 4th, 2024. With a focus on raising awareness about the monumental 30th session of the Conference of the Parties (COP 30), the 20th meeting of the COP serving as the Meeting of the Parties to the Kyoto Protocol (CMP 20), and the seventh meeting of the COP serving as the Meeting of the Parties to the Paris Agreement (CMA 7), this conference aims to galvanize student engagement in global climate action. Set against the backdrop of pressing environmental concerns, SCOP 30 provides a unique platform for students to immerse themselves in the intricacies of international climate negotiations. It offers a forum for participants to grasp the breadth and depth of discussions surrounding climate change and its far-reaching implications. The conference agenda is robust and comprehensive, reflecting the multifaceted nature of climate change and the diverse range of issues it encompasses. Anticipated key discussions will delve into topics such as Green Economics, Smart City Planning, the Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Environmental Protection, Intellectual Property and Environment, the inclusion of Environmental Protection in International Investment Treaty Provisions, and Sustainable Development. Through these dialogues, students will gain valuable insights into the complexities of environmental policymaking on a global scale. Participation in SCOP 30 offers students more than just an opportunity to expand their knowledge of environmental issues; it cultivates essential skills in diplomacy, negotiation, and collaboration. By engaging in meaningful discourse and exploring innovative solutions, students are poised to become catalysts for positive change in their communities and beyond. Ultimately, SCOP 30 serves as a beacon of hope, empowering the next generation of leaders to take bold and decisive action towards a more sustainable future. Through their collective efforts, students have the power to drive transformative change and pave the way for a healthier, more resilient planet for generations to come.

ABOUT ORGANISATION OF GREEN FUTURE AFGHANISTAN

The Organisation of Green Future Afghanistan stands as a beacon of hope and resilience in the realm of environmental protection and girls' empowerment. As an independent virtual NGO operating as a think tank dedicated to safeguarding Afghanistan's ecology, it takes immense pride in its unique status as the first girls' empowered NGO in the country, operating without financial support from any international entities or organizations. With a steadfast commitment to raising awareness and advocating for the protection of the Earth's precious resources, the

Organisation of Green Future Afghanistan orchestrates a myriad of academic events and conferences aimed at educating girls and providing platforms for them to shape their future. Founded by a group of like-minded students, the organization operates autonomously, free from any government affiliations or political activities. It staunchly condemns any claims or affiliations made by external entities and emphasizes its commitment to remaining independent and focused solely on its mission.

The dire need for environmental protection in Afghanistan cannot be overstated, particularly in light of the country's tumultuous history marked by decades of consecutive warfare. Despite Afghanistan's isolation and the overshadowing of its environmental concerns on the global stage, the Organisation of Green Future Afghanistan remains steadfast in its mission to shed light on the pressing environmental issues facing the nation.

The environmental degradation in Afghanistan is exacerbated by various factors, including the use of toxic chemicals by NATO and its allies, as well as by other state and non-state actors during decades of armed conflict. Moreover, the harsh winters compel citizens to resort to excessive fossil fuel usage, including burning car tires for warmth, further contributing to environmental degradation.

Furthermore, Afghanistan lacks comprehensive Environmental Impact Assessments, highlighting a critical gap in environmental governance. The Organisation of Green Future Afghanistan firmly believes that human rights encompass not only political freedoms but also the right to a healthy environment and sustainable livelihoods.

In the face of these challenges, the Organisation of Green Future Afghanistan remains steadfast in its commitment to championing environmental protection and girls' empowerment, calling for global attention and action to address the pressing environmental issues facing Afghanistan. Through education, advocacy, and grassroots activism, it strives to create a brighter, more sustainable future for all Afghans.

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DIGNITARIES

Chief Guest

Dr. N. Vanishree
Professor of Law
Chairman of Post Graduate
JSS Law College, Autonomous, Mysore
Karnataka, India

Guest of Honor

Prof. Banu M.

Professor of Computer Science
St Joseph University, Bengaluru-560027,
Karnataka, India

JUDGES

Dr. SRIDEVI KRISHNA **Professor of International Law**

Vidyavardhaka Law College
Sheshadri Iyer Road, New Bamboo Bazar,
Mysuru – 570001, Karnataka, India

ORGANISING MEMBERS

- **Ms Qadriya Hashimi**, CEO of the Organisation of Green Future Afghanistan and student of the [Institute of Legal and Policy Research \(Virtual NGO\)](#)
- **Ms Basmina Asghary**, Founding Member Organisation of Green Future Afghanistan student of the [Institute of Legal and Policy Research \(Virtual NGO\)](#)
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EXECUTIVE BOARD MEMBERS

Ms. Mrunalini Dnyaneshwar Borkar

Chairperson

Model United Nations Conference &
St Xavier's High School, MIDC NAGPUR,

Ms. Saba Firdose
Rapporteur,
Model United Nations Conference &
Student of LLM, Department of Studies in Law
University of Mysore.
Email: sabamubarakkhan@gmail.com

Contact Information

For inquiries and participation confirmation, please contact the following undersigned:

INTERNATIONAL MODEL UNITED NATIONS CONFERENCE- 2024 (STUDENTS' COP 30 IN AFGHANISTAN)

Organiser: Organisation of Green Future Afghanistan

Agenda: Critical discussions are anticipated to revolve around various topics, including Green Economics, Smart City Planning, the Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Environmental Protection, Intellectual Property and Environment, Sustainable Development and inclusion of Environmental Protection in International Investment Treaty Provisions.

Event: 4th May, 2024.

Participants: Participation is open exclusively to females worldwide.

Format & Platform: Webex (Online)

Registration Fees: None (This event is free of charge)

Registration Links: <https://forms.gle/hSJJSft3EeYkFysE7>

Certificates: Digital certificates with QR code verification will be awarded based on active participation.

DIGNITARIES

CHIEF GUEST

Dr. N. Vanishree

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Chairman of Post Graduate

JSS Law College, Autonomous, Mysore

Karnataka, India

GUEST OF HONOR

Prof. Banu M.

Assistant Professor of Computer Science

St Joseph University,

Bengaluru-560027, Karnataka, India

JUDGES

Dr. SRIDEVI KRISHNA
Professor of International Law
Vidyavardhaka Law College
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Student of LLM, Department of Studies in Law
University of Mysore.

Email: sabamubarakkhan@gmail.com

Contact Information

For inquiries and participation confirmation, please contact the following undersigned:

Ms. Qadriya Hashimi
CEO
Organisation of Green Future Afghanistan
Email: info@ogfaf.org
Website: <https://www.ogfaf.org/>

**International Model United Nations Conference- 2024 (Students' COP 30 in
Afghanistan)**

Country Matrix

Serial No.	Country	Name	Institution	Mobile no.
1	Afghanistan			
2	Albania			
3	Algeria			
4	Andorra			
5	Angola			
6	Antigua and Barbuda			
7	Argentina			
8	Armenia			
9	Australia			
10	Austria			
11	Azerbaijan			
12	Bahamas			
13	Bahrain			
14	Bangladesh			
15	Barbados			
16	Belarus			
17	Belgium			
18	Belize			
19	Benin			
20	Bhutan			
21	Bolivia			
22	Bosnia and Herzegovina			
23	Botswana			
24	Brazil			
25	Brunei			
26	Bulgaria			
27	Burkina Faso			
28	Burundi			
29	Côte d'Ivoire			
30	Cabo Verde			
31	Cambodia			

32	Cameroon			
33	Canada			
34	Central African Republic			
35	Chad			
36	Chile			
37	China			
38	Colombia			
39	Comoros			
40	Congo (Congo-Brazzaville)			
41	Costa Rica			
42	Croatia			
43	Cuba			
44	Cyprus			
45	Czechia (Czech Republic)			
46	Democratic Republic of the Congo			
47	Denmark			
48	Djibouti			
49	Dominica			
50	Dominican Republic			
51	Ecuador			
52	Egypt			
53	El Salvador			
54	Equatorial Guinea			
55	Eritrea			
56	Estonia			
57	Eswatini (fmr. "Swaziland")			
58	Ethiopia			
59	Fiji			
60	Finland			
61	France			
62	Gabon			
63	Gambia			
64	Georgia			
65	Germany			
66	Ghana			
67	Greece			

68	Grenada			
69	Guatemala			
70	Guinea			
71	Guinea-Bissau			
72	Guyana			
73	Haiti			
74	Holy See			
75	Honduras			
76	Hungary			
77	Iceland			
78	India			
79	Indonesia			
80	Iran			
81	Iraq			
82	Ireland			
83	Israel			
84	Italy			
85	Jamaica			
86	Japan			
87	Jordan			
88	Kazakhstan			
89	Kenya			
90	Kiribati			
91	Kuwait			
92	Kyrgyzstan			
93	Laos			
94	Latvia			
95	Lebanon			
96	Lesotho			
97	Liberia			
98	Libya			
99	Liechtenstein			
100	Lithuania			
101	Luxembourg			
102	Madagascar			
103	Malawi			
104	Malaysia			
105	Maldives			
106	Mali			
107	Malta			
108	Marshall Islands			
109	Mauritania			
110	Mauritius			
111	Mexico			

112	Micronesia			
113	Moldova			
114	Monaco			
115	Mongolia			
116	Montenegro			
117	Morocco			
118	Mozambique			
119	Myanmar			
120	Namibia			
121	Nauru			
122	Nepal			
123	Netherlands			
124	New Zealand			
125	Nicaragua			
126	Niger			
127	Nigeria			
128	North Korea			
129	North Macedonia			
130	Norway			
131	Oman			
132	Pakistan			
133	Palau			
134	Palestine State			
135	Panama			
136	Papua New Guinea			
137	Paraguay			
138	Peru			
139	Philippines			
140	Poland			
141	Portugal			
142	Qatar			
143	Romania			
144	Russia			
145	Rwanda			
146	Saint Kitts and Nevis			
147	Saint Lucia			
148	Saint Vincent and the Grenadines			
149	Samoa			
150	San Marino			
151	Sao Tome and Principe			

152	Saudi Arabia			
153	Senegal			
154	Serbia			
155	Seychelles			
156	Sierra Leone			
157	Singapore			
158	Slovakia			
159	Slovenia			
160	Solomon Islands			
161	Somalia			
162	South Africa			
163	South Korea			
164	South Sudan			
165	Spain			
166	Sri Lanka			
167	Sudan			
168	Suriname			
169	Sweden			
170	Switzerland			
171	Syria			
172	Tajikistan			
173	Tanzania			
174	Thailand			
175	Timor-Leste			
176	Togo			
177	Tonga			
178	Trinidad and Tobago			
179	Tunisia			
180	Turkey			
181	Turkmenistan			
182	Tuvalu			
183	Uganda			
184	Ukraine			
185	United Arab Emirates			
186	United Kingdom			
187	United States of America			
188	Uruguay			
189	Uzbekistan			
190	Vanuatu			
191	Venezuela			
192	Vietnam			
193	Yemen			

194	Zambia			
195	Zimbabwe			

Participants can choose the country from the country matrix. Each participant will be allowed to represent only one country. Countries will be allotted according to preference on a first come, first serve basis.

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